

On the Indirect Application of Radiocative Nuclei in Analytical Chemistry. Part II

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Sc^{46} has been used to examine the validity of the methods for estimating scandium. The method, based on the precipitation of scandium as hydroxide and its subsequent ignition, has been found to be a dependable one. Scandium even in sulphuric acid medium undergoes complete hydrolysis when boiled with a mixture of iodate and iodide. The iodine liberated in the process can be collected and estimated either by hypo titration or by radiometric method with I^{131} . In case of radiometric procedure, scandium up to 0.09 mg. can be estimated with a fair degree of accuracy. Using labelled pyrophosphate ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}^{32}_2\text{O}_7$) scandium up to 0.9 mg. has been estimated within statistical fluctuation. Rare earths do not interfere in the estimation of scandium as pyrophosphate.

Analytical aspect of the chemistry of this element faces controversy. According to Bock and Fischer¹, precipitation of scandium as hydroxide or as basic tartrate and its subsequent ignition to Sc_2O_3 is a dependable method. Schoeller and Powell² also commented in favour of the procedure. Vickery³ challenged all earlier observations and categorically stated that there was no reliable method for the estimation of scandium. He made use of Sc^{46} as an indicator in most of his findings. Because of these uncertainties, as pointed out above, an attempt has been made to examine the earlier methods and find out simplified procedures for the estimation of scandium, using in most cases radioactive indicator for the purpose.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation of scandium was undertaken in different ways: as hydroxide by precipitating with ammonia, as pyrophosphate with radioactive phosphorus (P-32) and also in an indirect way by allowing hydrolysis of scandium salts to completion with iodate and iodide and estimating the iodine liberated in the process either by hypo or in trace quantities by radiometric estimation as developed by us⁴ for estimating very small quantities of iodine, silver, and aluminium. Practical procedures in case of scandium will be discussed later.

Scandium oxide of spect. pure quality, as supplied by Messrs. Johnson & Methey Co. Ltd., was taken as a primary standard. It was ignited to a constant weight and then dissolved in HCl (conc.). Scandium activity was added to it as a measuring indicator and the solution was converted to hydroxide by iodate and iodide. It was then washed free of iodide by double distilled water. No scandium loss was observed. This was then dissolved in a known amount of sulphuric acid and a stock solution for the study of scandium estimation by hydrolysis was thus made. An aliquot portion was taken in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a standard glass joint and distillation was carried out as in the

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1942, 249, 146.
2. "Analysis of Minerals & Ores of the Rarer Elements", Charles Griffin & Co. Ltd., London, 1955, p. 73.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3113.
4. *This Journal*, 1957, 34, 487.

case of aluminium⁴. The whole procedure was the same as in the case of aluminium as regards reagents and other conditions. Data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

**Estimation of scandium by the use of I¹³¹.*

Scandium.		Standard deviations in activity measurements.	Amount of iodate and iodide used in 300 ml.
Taken.	Found.		
0.965 mg.	0.980 mg.	± 2.2 %	0.5g. KI + 0.5g. KIO ₃
0.965	0.951	± 2.4	"
0.209	0.211	± 3.1	"
0.098	0.099	± 2.0	"
0.098	0.094	± 2.0	"
0.096	0.096	± 2.2	"
0.090	0.091	± 2.3	"

*Iodine was collected in a solution of sodium sulphite and sodium carbonate and slowly neutralised. Nearly one third equivalent of known silver was added and silver iodide was carried by zirconium phosphate following the same procedure as described in our previous work⁴.

A general stock solution was prepared as follows: Scandium oxide of the specification as stated above was ignited to a constant weight and then dissolved in HCl (conc.). An aliquot portion was taken and gaseous ammonia was passed through it till the solution was yellow to methyl red. It was filtered and washed with hot ammonium nitrate solution, made just yellow to methyl red by addition of ammonia till free of chloride, and ignited as usual to Sc₂O₃. Effect of excess of ammonium ions (Table II) was also studied to ensure guaranteed success. Sc⁴⁶ was used as a tracer to detect the loss of scandium in the operation. Data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

*Estimation of scandium by precipitating as hydroxide using gaseous ammonia.**

	Scandium oxide.		Scandium activity (Sc ⁴⁶ in terms of counts/min.).		Experimental conditions.
	Taken.	Found.	Added.	Found.**	
1.	25.60 mg.		27120 c/m ±1.0%	40 c/m ±1.5%	NH ₄ Cl added=5 g. Vol. = 40 ml. Filtered through sintered glass.
2.	25.60		27120 c/m ±1.0%	50 c/m ±1.5%	NH ₄ Cl added=2.0g. Vol. = 60 ml. Filtration through filter paper.
3.	25.60		27120 c/m 1.0 %	60 c/m ±1.5%	Conditions same as (1). Separation done through centrifugation.
4.	143.50	142.70 mg.	32440 c/m ±1.0%	10 c/m ±2.2%	NH ₄ Cl added=0.5g. Vol.=100 ml.
5.	167.90	168.41	32408 c/m ±1.2%	12 c/m ±2.3%	Do
6.	178.30	177.70	32435 c/m ±1.0%	15 c/m ±2.2%	Do
7.	84.36	83.98	32435 c/m ±1.0%	21 c/m ±2.3%	Do

*In all these operations highest amount of scandium activity remaining in solution does not exceed 0.25%. Error on the estimation by ignition to oxide is always below 0.5%. The method is therefore perfectly dependable.

**In the filtrate after washing the ppt. till free of chloride.

From Table II the method appears to be quite dependable.

Disodium hydrogen phosphate was taken and a stock solution was prepared. Phosphate was estimated as magnesium pyrophosphate. An aliquot portion was taken in a crucible and carrier-free P-32 as Na_2HPO_4 was added to it. It was then evaporated to dryness and heated at 500° for 5 hours⁵. Conversion to pyrophosphate was confirmed by measuring the loss in weight on ignition. Calculations were done from the theoretical amount taken. About twice the theoretical amount required by the formula⁶ ScHP_2O_7 of the pyrophosphate solution was taken in a centrifuge tube. A known volume of scandium solution (acidity 0.2N) was added. It was slightly warmed and allowed to coagulate. The precipitate was settled by centrifugation. A fraction of this volume was taken and the phosphorus activity was measured by a liquid counter in the usual way. From the loss in activity, the quantity of scandium was determined. In case of small amounts, about 50 mg. of barium sulphate was precipitated in the medium. Amongst the interfering ions, cerium(ous) was selected because of the frequent association of scandium with rare earth minerals. Details are recorded in Tables III A and IIIB.

TABLE IIIA

Estimation of scandium as pyrophosphate using P-32.

Scandium.		Standard deviations in activity measurements.	Experimental conditions.
Taken.	Found.		
10.94 mg.	10.86 mg.	$\pm 2.5\%$	Vol. = 40 ml; acidity = 0.2N- H_2SO_4 .
6.04	6.16	± 2.5	Do
6.43	6.44	± 2.0	Do
4.78	4.89		Vol. = 20 ml; acidity = 0.2N- H_2SO_4 BaSO_4 was used as a collector ($\approx 125\text{mg.}$)
4.78	4.69	± 2.1	Do
2.20	2.17	± 2.3	Vol. = 10 ml; acidity = 0.2N- H_2SO_4 , BaSO_4 was used as a collector ($\approx 60\text{ mg.}$)
2.20	2.10	± 2.0	Do
2.20	2.30	± 2.0	Do
1.64	1.55	± 2.5	Vol. = 10 ml; acidity = 0.2N- H_2SO_4 . BaSO_4 was used as a collector ($\approx 60\text{ mg.}$)
1.640	1.590	± 3.0	Do
0.956	0.946	± 2.0	Vol. = 4 ml; acidity = 0.2N- H_2SO_4 . BaSO_4 was used as a collector ($\approx 25\text{ mg.}$)
0.956	0.937	± 2.0	Do
0.956	0.971	± 2.4	Do
0.901	0.911	± 2.5	Do
0.901	0.924	± 1.9	Do
0.901	0.900	± 2.0	Do

5. Audrieth, "Inorganic Synthesis", Vol. III, McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc., 1950, p. 100.
6. Beck, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1949, 34, 282.

TABLE IIB

**In presence of ceric ion.*

S c a n d i u m.		Standard deviations in activity measurements.	Cerium added.
Taken.	Found.		
4.78 mg.	4.71 mg.	$\pm 3.2\%$	0.10 mg
4.78	4.68	± 1.9	4.80
4.78	4.69	± 2.0	4.80
4.78	4.72	± 2.2	6.40
4.78	4.77	± 2.5	9.60
4.78	4.64	± 2.4	9.60

*Tetravalent cerium was reduced to trivalent state with hydrogen peroxide.

DISCUSSION

Tables I-III show that three different procedures have been adopted for estimating scandium. It was Vickery³ who pointed out that estimation of scandium by ammonia in the presence of ammonium salts led to erroneous results. His results, however, refer to very concentrated scandium solutions where there may be causes for such interference. But in day-to-day routine chemical analysis, one does not encounter such concentrated solutions. Table II shows that precipitation by gaseous ammonia and its subsequent ignition to oxide is an accurate and reliable method of analysis. In the present investigation, a big stock of scandium was not available and therefore the conditions under which Vickery got low results could not be repeated.

Scandium was also estimated by iodometric estimation by allowing hydrolysis of scandium salts to completion, as was done in the case of aluminium⁴. The results are always within statistical fluctuations. It can be used in case of simple scandium compounds in a very dilute sulphuric acid medium where acid concentration is known.

Use of labelled pyrophosphate in analysis is rather much less troublesome than that of labelled phosphate, which is so popular. It has been observed during the present investigation that pyrophosphate is not adsorbed on glass surfaces. As an interfering ion cerium, which was reduced to 'ous' state with hydrogen peroxide, was used. It has been found that larger amounts of cerium (twice) did not interfere with estimation. Scandium pyrophosphate was described by Beck⁵ as an insoluble compound. Its application to the estimation of scandium had not, however, been attempted. Because of its insolubility in mineral acids ($\sim 0.1N$) and because of the fact that pyrophosphates of most of the elements are soluble in acidic medium, attempt has been made in the present work to use labelled sodium pyrophosphate for the radiometric estimation of scandium. As a matter of fact, larger quantities of $Na_4P_2O_7$ of high specific activity can be prepared from disodium hydrogen phosphate. A portion can be weighed and dissolved in known volume from which an aliquot portion can be added in the estimation. It has been observed by us that in a day pyrophosphate

solution does not hydrolyse appreciably. Table III (A and B) shows that the method provides results always within statistical fluctuations. Scandium can be estimated with a fair degree of accuracy in presence of many of the elements which interfere in other methods.

From this study with radioactive indicators, it can be inferred that the method which has been examined and the procedures which have been developed by us are quite dependable in the estimation of scandium.

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